

Supplementary Table 1—DXA Body Composition Data Excluding Participant #2*

	Pre-LGL Diet	Post-LGL Diet	p-value
Weight (kg)	65.1 ± 3.7	64.3 ± 3.5	0.23
BMI (kg/m ²)	24.1 ± 0.7	23.7 ± 0.6	0.22
Total fat mass (gm)	23173 ± 3096	21849 ± 3273	0.05
Total lean mass (gm)	44307 ± 4379	44392 ± 44493	0.86
% fat mass	33.6 ± 4.2	32.3 ± 4.5	0.02
Trunk fat (gm)	10405 ± 1668	9746 ± 1733	0.05
% trunk fat	30.4 ± 4.2	29.2 ± 4.6	0.05
Fat mass index (FMI, kg/m ²)	8.5 ± 1.2	8.1 ± 1.3	0.08
Lean mass index (LMI, kg/m ²)	15.8 ± 0.9	15.9 ± 1.0	0.56
Appendicular lean mass index (ALMI, kg/m ²)	6.5 ± 0.5	6.6 ± 0.5	0.41

*Participant #2 stopped exercising 4-6 times weekly mid-study

Bolded values represent $p \leq 0.05$

BMI, body mass index

Supplementary Table 2—Biochemical Data

	Pre-LGL Diet	Post-LGL Diet	p-value
ESR (mm/h)	15.9 ± 6.9	13.7 ± 5.3	0.77
CRP (mg/L)	0.16 ± 0.06	0.20 ± 0.07	0.26
HbA1c (%)	5.7 ± 0.2	5.7 ± 0.2	0.55

ESR, erythrocyte sedimentation rate; CRP, c-reactive protein; HbA1c, hemoglobin A1c

Supplementary Table 3—Detailed Participant Weight Data

ID	Start Weight (kg)	End Weight (kg)	Lowest Weight (kg)	Absolute Change (kg)	% Change
1	55.2	55.6	54.9	0.4	-0.7
2	61.4	61.8	59.7	0.4	0.6
4	78.0	74.1	72.8	-3.9	-5.0
5	60.3	61.2	61.2	0.9	1.5
6	49.0	49.7	49.2	0.7	1.4
7	69.3	69.2	68.0	-0.1	-0.2
8	56.0	55.8	55.8	-0.2	-0.4
9	80.5	81.2	81.7	0.7	0.9
10	75.3	73.3	72.4	-2.0	-2.7
11	62.7	58.3	58.3	-4.4	-7.0*
Average	63.7	63.6	62.9	-0.8	-0.5

*After study completion, participant 11 disclosed intentionally trying to lose weight mid-study

Supplemental Figure 1— Diet Tolerability Questionnaire

SECTION A: GENERAL INFORMATION

A1. Study ID Number: ____

A2. Date of Visit: ____ / ____ / ____
M M D D Y Y Y Y

A3. Initials of person completing form: _____

SECTION B: SATISFACTION

For each of the 5 questions below, please circle a number to indicate your response.

B1. How satisfied are you with this diet overall?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
Completely Extremely
Unsatisfied Satisfied

B2. How well did this diet satisfy your hunger?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
Extremely Completely
Hungry Satisfied

B3. How easy has this diet been?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
Extremely Extremely
Difficult Easy

B4. How tasty have the foods been on this diet?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
Extremely Extremely
Tasteless Tasty

B5. How strongly would you recommend this diet to others?

1 2 3 4 5 6 7 8 9 10
Not Completely
Recommend Recommend

Total: _____

Supplemental Figure 2— Study Timeline Diagram:

CGM, continuous glucose monitor; V#, visit number; LGL, low glycemic load